

From BIM to Asset Management – data-driven guidelines for Operations Maintenance

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Abstract

BIM is increasingly considered as a key driver in the design, manufacturing, and management of digital information in the AECO/O industry. The tridimensional visualization combined with the data collection allows for a comprehensive understanding of assets, enabling continuous development, and launching a learning cycle for the built environment.

Out of all work stages of a building, the operations and maintenance phase, often known as the “in use” phase, is flagged as the major cost in its lifecycle. Hunting relevant data for Facility Management (FM) may absorb over than 80% of the teams available time.

BIM integration can assist the FM industry, by acting as a dynamic data pool evolving from preliminary stages of Design, BIM develops into a complete solution for FM, capable of boosting workflows by using recent technologies combined with data-driven processes.

Surrounded by a swarm of software providers, the industry has been claiming the challenge of determining which tools to effectively transmit information to the FM stage. Out of the potential procedures that enable BIM-FM linking practices, a structured data delivery procedure can be found, offered by the open exchange protocol COBie. COBie stands out

as a vendor-neutral tool, capable of data bridging between Design and subsequent stages, as it can be exported from a BIM authoring tool and loaded into Digital Asset Management solutions. Additionally, it liberates owners and operators to deploy different maintenance systems, while providing reliable and accurate data.

Given that the lack of a clear framework continues to hinder BIM data awareness for integration inside facilities management, the expected outcome of this dissertation is the development of a comprehensive COBie guide, a tool cable to assist teams in producing valid COBie deliverables.

A case study was used to implement the developed tool, in collaboration with a business partner, LIMSEN Consulting. The tool development, evaluation, and validation consist of the three major phases of the procedure intended to provide clear information requirements, responsibilities, and data drops. Finally, the presented work aims to strengthen the industry's readiness to transition from document-oriented practices into model-based, data-driven automated processes.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/HwTVQ-IHPng>

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